

Consumption Expenditure Disparities of Indian Families

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.20592599

Abstract:

Income and consumption are two fundamental aspects of household economic behaviours. In India, family income determines the level and pattern of consumption expenditure on goods and services such as food, housing, education, and healthcare. This paper examines the consumption patterns in Indian families, focusing on rural–urban differences, changes in consumption behaviour, and recent trends. The study shows that rising income levels in India have led to increased consumption expenditure and a shift from food-based spending to non-food items such as education, health, transport, and durable goods.

Keywords: *Household, Consumption Expenditure, Monthly Per Capita Consumption Expenditure (MPCE), Rural and Urban.*

Introduction:

Household income and consumption are central to understanding economic welfare and living standards. Income represents the earnings received by households through wages, business profits, or transfers, while consumption refers to the spending on goods and services to satisfy needs and wants. In India, consumption patterns are strongly influenced by factors such as: Income level, Family size, Education and occupation, Rural–urban differences, Government policies and welfare schemes. As income rises, families generally increase their consumption expenditure and diversify their spending toward better quality goods and services.

Objectives of the Study:

The main objectives of this study are:

1. To analyze consumption expenditure patterns of households.
2. To analyze differences between rural and urban consumption patterns.

Research Methodology:

The study is based on secondary data sources, including: Household Consumption Expenditure Survey (HCES), Reports of the Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation (MOSPI). For the analysis, percentage tool is used. The Period of 2022-23 has been selected for present research paper.

Analysis:

1. Income of Indian Families:

Income of Indian households comes from salaries and wages, agriculture and allied activities, business or self-employment, government transfers and welfare schemes, investment and remittances. After 1991, Household incomes in India have gradually increased because of economic growth, urbanization and employment opportunities. However, income and property inequality exists between rural and urban house, different district, state and social groups

2. Trend in MPCE since 1999-'00, All-India:

Table No. 1: Trend in MPCE since 1999-'00, All-India

Sector	Average MPCE (Rs.) in				
	1999-'00 NSS (55 th round)	2004-05 NSS (61 st round)	2009-10 NSS (66 th round)	2011-12 NSS (68 th round)	2022-23
At nominal price					
Rural	486	579	1,054	1,430	3,773
Urban	855	1,105	1,984	2,630	6,459
At real price (2011-12 price)					
Rural	978	1,054	1,239	1,430	2,008
Urban	1,823	1,946	2,358	2,630	3,510

Source: Survey On Household Consumption Expenditure 2022-23

Table No. 1 shows Trend in MPCE since 1999-'00, All-India. Consumption expenditure refers to the amount spent by households on goods and services. According to the Household Consumption Expenditure Survey (2022-23), Average monthly per capita consumption

expenditure (MPCE) in India is about ₹4,534. Rural MPCE is around ₹3,733, while urban MPCE is about ₹6,459. Urban families spend significantly more than rural families due to higher income and living costs.

3. Food and Non-Food Consumption Expenditure Trends in India:

Table 2: Food and Non-Food Consumption Expenditure Trends in India

Item group	Average MPCE (Rs.)		Percentage share in total MPCE (%)	
	Rural	Urban	Rural	Urban
food total	1,750	2,530	46.38	39.17
non-food total	2,023	3,929	53.62	60.83
all items	3,773	6,459	100.00	100.00

Source: Survey On Household Consumption Expenditure 2022-23

Table No. 2 shows Food and Non-Food Consumption Expenditure Trends in India. Rural households spend 46.38% on food, while urban households spend 39.17%, indicating a significant

shift toward services, mobility, and lifestyle goods in cities. Non-food items account for 53.62% of rural and 60.83% of urban spending, a major increase in the last two decades.

4. Comparison of average MPCE across social groups in 2022-23:

Table No. 3: Comparison of average MPCE across social groups in 2022-23

Social Group	Rural	Urban
ST	3,098	5,472
SC	3,571	5,386
OBC	3,935	6,245
General	4,472	7,382
all	3,860	6,521

Source: Survey On Household Consumption Expenditure 2022-23

Table No. 3 shows Comparison of average MPCE across social groups in 2022-23. The average MPCE for Scheduled Tribes was Rs.3098 in rural area and Rs. 5472 in urban areas in 2022-23, when the average MPCE for General category was Rs. 4472 in rural area and Rs. 7382 in urban areas. The average MPCE for OBC category was more than SC category both rural and urban but less than general category. For every social group, urban MPCE is significantly higher than rural MPCE, though the gap is narrowing overall.

5. Comparison of average MPCE across religions in 2022-23:

Table No. 4: Comparison of average MPCE across religions in 2022-23

Sr.	Region	MPCE (Rs)
1	Muslim	4047
2	Buddhism	4345
3	Hinduism	4544
4	Christianity	5739
5	Sikhism	5920
6	Jainism	7861

Source: <https://www.dataforindia.com>

Table No. 4 shows comparison of average MPCE across religions in 2022-23. The lowest average MPCE was Rs. 4047 for Muslim. The lowest average MPCE for Muslim is indicating higher levels of poverty and lower consumption expenditure compared to other religious communities. The average MPCE for Jainism was Rs.7861, which highest in India. The average MPCE for Hinduism was Rs. 4544 which more than Muslim and Buddhism but less than Christianity, Sikhism and Jainism.

Conclusion:

The study concludes that income plays a crucial role in determining the consumption patterns of Indian families. Rising income levels have increased household expenditure and diversified consumption patterns. While food still accounts for a significant share of spending, there is a clear shift toward non-food items such as education, healthcare, and durable goods. However, disparities between rural and urban households remain significant. Policymakers must focus on inclusive growth to improve income levels and consumption capacity across all sections of society.

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